

IMPROVING ECOLOGICAL EDUCATION IN NATURAL GEOGRAPHY

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Abstract: *This article is about the important peculiarities of improving ecological education in natural geography. Furthermore, different approaches and benefits of teaching environmental education were given.*

Key Words: *environmental education, multi-disciplinary, traditional [K-12 curriculum](#), Green school, Health Benefits, Future proof planning .*

Education is the most powerful and dominant influence which one can use to change the world, perhaps proven by many other scholars around the world which is why we need to educate ourselves about the importance of environmental education in order to make the world a better place to live in. Before going deep into environmental education, we will understand the concept behind it all together. Let us remind ourselves that we are responsible for how we shape our environment because only by creating awareness about the harmful effects of [environmental damage](#) can help us build a safe and secure future for our children. When we are educated about the environment, we must identify our responsibility as global citizens and make a positive change for our planet earth which will help us utilize our resources more efficiently and without harming our environment as well. Environmental education (EE) refers to organized efforts to teach how natural environments function, and particularly, how human beings can manage behavior and [ecosystems](#) to [live sustainably](#). It is a multi-disciplinary field integrating disciplines such as biology, chemistry, physics, ecology, earth science, atmospheric science, mathematics, and geography. The [United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organisation](#) (UNESCO) states that EE is vital in imparting an inherent respect for nature among society and in enhancing public environmental awareness. UNESCO emphasises the role of EE in safeguarding future global developments of societal [quality of life](#) (QOL), through the protection of the environment, eradication of

poverty, minimization of inequalities and insurance of sustainable development.

The term often implies education within the school system, from primary to post-secondary. However, it sometimes includes all efforts to educate the public and other audiences, including print materials, websites, media campaigns, etc.. There are also ways that environmental education is taught outside the traditional classroom. Aquariums, zoos, parks, and nature centers all have ways of teaching the public about the environment. Environmental education has been considered an additional or elective subject in much of traditional [K-12 curriculum](#). At the [elementary school](#) level, environmental education can take the form of [science](#) enrichment curriculum, [natural history](#) field trips, community service projects, and participation in outdoor science schools. EE policies assist schools and organizations in developing and improving environmental education programs that provide citizens with an in-depth understanding of the environment. School related EE policies focus on three main components: curricula, green facilities, and training. Schools can integrate environmental education into their curricula with sufficient funding from EE policies. This approach – known as using the “environment as an integrating context” for learning – uses the local environment as a framework for teaching state and district education standards. In addition to funding environmental curricula in the classroom, environmental education policies allot the financial resources for hands-on, outdoor learning. These activities and lessons help address and mitigate "[nature deficit disorder](#)", as well as encourage healthier lifestyles. Green schools, or green facility promotion, are another main component of environmental education policies. Greening school facilities cost, on average, a little less than 2 percent more than creating a traditional school, but payback from these [energy efficient buildings](#) occur within only a few years. Environmental education policies help reduce the relatively small burden of the initial start-up costs for green schools. Green school policies also provide grants for modernization, renovation, or repair of older school facilities. Additionally, healthy food options are also a central aspect of green schools. These policies specifically focus on bringing freshly prepared food, made from high-quality, locally grown ingredients into schools. There are many benefits of teaching environmental education. Now we will see some of them.

✓ Educational Achievements – By providing environmental education to students they will engage problem-solving techniques of the

outer world to their subjects to understand a particular problem by implying outdoor environmental solutions.

✓ Health Benefits – Environmental Education gives students a new meaning to exploring mother nature to see and resolve the issues which are harmful to the environment and this will also help them in maintaining their own health by doing physical work so that their bodies will be immune from some serious health issues such as short-sightedness, obesity and in some cases even lack concentration.

✓ Future proof planning – This is one of the issues which we need to deal with because if we don't educate our kids about the hazardous effects of environmental damage there will be no future of the world. Education in this field will give students a new meaning to problem-solving techniques as they will solve real-world problems. They will also think beyond today for becoming future proof and investigate the situation carefully and take preventive measures in the future for environmental safeguarding.

✓ Managing teams – Working in teams is another example of Environmental education as it gives kids a new meaning to solve a certain problem by doing teamwork.

This will also bring out the leadership qualities in them as they will lead the path for their team to stop people from throwing garbage anywhere and also spread awareness to other people that use only non-plastic goods for the betterment of the environment. The use of plastic is one of the big environmental issues in the past few decades. We can reduce the plastic accumulation to some extent if we stop using at least single-use plastic. This small step can make a big difference to deal with this environmental issue. When we educate students about the environment and motivate them to take initiative to protect it as a major part of their life they will become activist for the environment and stop others from harming the environment by creating platforms for the awareness of the need and importance of environmental education in every part of the society. Nowadays there are a lot of distractions in a society which diverts the attention of students from their education to some other side. By educating them about the environment they will be able to focus more on real-world problems as they are the ones who will be analyzing and solving the problems of the environment to [promote more greenery](#) everywhere.

Environmental Education is more of the responsibility which is to be done every day by students as well as teachers which will encourage them to go out and take practical activities as to [how to conserve energy](#) and

environment. It will also help them to explore and learn new innovative techniques that will help them understand conservation more easily. By learning how to protect the environment students need to participate in maintaining the school premises as well because it is better to start first where you actually belong i.e. school and home. It will be very beneficial for schools as it will reduce the maintenance cost of the surrounding which will automatically cut back on the annual cost of overall expenses. Motivate your kids to switch off the electric switches and other appliances when not using it, make your kids aware of the 3 R's i.e. [Reduce Reuse & Recycle](#), encourage them to close the taps after use to save water, etc. If more organizations will adopt environmental education as their priority then there will be more kids as well as adults who will help in conserving the environment and also help in creating more awareness amongst others.

The global youth is playing an important role in spreading awareness about environmental issues worldwide. For example– In 2017, a student activist from the University of Sussex named Paris Palmano had set up "Climate Action Movement". The main objective of this movement was to spread awareness of climate crisis and possible preventive measures to [deal with climate change](#). There is another example from India where the students of Great-men International School, Madhya Pradesh has taken initiative in 2010 to plant almost 1100 sapling to save the environment. There are many other examples where the students from different schools have taken the initiative to protect mother Earth.

To sum up, it should be highlighted that educational institutes are very important to start teaching students how to safeguard our environment and [save natural resources](#). There are various measures that are used by organizations by using the latest technology and advancement in conserving the environment and also help them in promoting the huge online campaign to create awareness on this matter, which will bring people together on the environment education promotion. Environmental Education helps in building the natural world, gives knowledge and method to solve complex environmental issues which also gives advancement to productive economies and harmony among communities.

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